

HEALTH CARE PROFESSIONAL PERCEPTION TOWARDS ENGAGEMENT FACTORS WITH REFERENCE TO MULTI- SPECIALTY HOSPITAL IN CHENNAI

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the health care professional perception towards their job engagement with special reference to multispecialty hospital in Chennai. Job engagement factors such as meaningful work, intrinsic rewards, extrinsic rewards, and self-efficacy, departmental support, supervisor support, co-worker support, job autonomy and job security are considered for this study. Questionnaire has been constructed the above said factors based on the past research work. Questionnaire has been used to collect the primary data from the health care professional working in multispecialty hospital in Chennai. A sample of 180 employees are approached to participate in the survey through convenience sampling method. The collected data are analysed with descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation. The findings of the study reflected the employees are having higher level of engagement in their job. Here, extrinsic reward, self-efficacy, departmental support, and job autonomy are the engagement factors found to be high among the healthcare professional. It is implied that among the healthcare professional. It is implied that engagement is the capacity of employees work endeavour, obligation and aspiration enduring in the organization.

Keywords: Employees Engagement, Healthcare Professional, Perception, Multispecialty Hospital, Chennai.

INTRODUCTION

Employee engagement is the key focus of both business entrepreneurs and academic researchers and is blistering issue of modern business environment. Every organization wants to gain competitive advantages over others and employee engagement is the best tool for it. In fact, employee engagement is considered to be the most powerful factor to Measure Company's vigor (Baumruk, 2004). Engagement is creating prospect for human resources to attach with their managers, colleagues and organization. It's concern is to shape a milieu where employees are motivated and connected with their job in real caring manner to do a high-quality job.

Engagement is a perception that places continuous improvement, change and flexibility at the empathy of what it means. So an employee as well as an employer must understand the twenty-first-century workplace requirements. Cindy (2008) stated that engagement is the capacity of employee's work endeavour, obligation and aspiration enduring in a business. Decision Making or Coordination is an important variable bearing an influencing role and creating effect on employee engagement (Konrad, Alison 2006).

Performance of engaged employees lead the company towards customer satisfaction which ultimately direct an organization towards profitability (Bassi, Laurie 2010). In the modern business anticipate their employees should be positive and take responsibility for developing their expertise. They are expected to be devoted to excellent performance appraisal standards. Organizations needed employees who are active, committed and enthralled to their job.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Penna research report (2007) stated that meaning of work has the potential to be available way of bringing employers and employees closer together to the benefit of both where employees experience a sense of community, the space to be themselves and the opportunity to make a contribution, they find meaning. Employees want to work in the organizations in which they find meaning at work.

Marcie Pitt et al. (2009) found that the following factors related to employee's characteristics such a gender, household income, elder care status, physical health, mental health, core self-evaluation and ageand work experience of employee.

Thiagarajan and Renugadevi (2011) said that the motivation factors and performance appraisal are associated to employee engagement. The consequences are that leaders should be culturedon engagement, career development opportunities which are most important and that performance improvements should champion work life balance, and these practices are useful to rise engagement levels.

Bhatla's (2011) highlighted the importance of measuring employee engagement is to make them feel valuable and continue working on employee engagement practices like providing career opportunities, safety, training and development, communication and leadership enhance employee performance in the organization.

Madhura Bedarkar and Deepika Pandita (2013) stated that employee engagement is a concept gaining significant importance in the past 10 years. The concept of employee engagement has now gained even more importance, since many drivers have been identified, which impact employee performance and well-being at workplace.

Nusrat Khan (2013) found that there are several drivers for engagement which vary by industry, job functions, and group and job level. Good quality line management, two way open communication, effective cooperation, focus on developing employees and their wellbeing, fair pay and benefits, good HR practices in place and a harmonious work environment.

Samuel Obino Mokayo and Maureen Jerotich kipyegon (2014) identified that remuneration is the highest contributor of employee engagement and recreation facilities has least impact on employee engagement.

Vijay Anand and C.vijay Banu (2016) explained that employee engagement is the key factor for all organizations to sustain. Employee Engagement is positively influenced by job, Rewards and recognition, opportunities, team work and communication are acted as a retention tool.

Research Problem

Employee engagement is a critical ingredient of individual and organizational success. It predicts employee outcomes, organizational success and financial performance. The impact of engagement can manifest itself through productivity and outcomes for customers of the organisation, employee retention rates, organizational culture and advocacy of the organisation and its external image (Schaufeli and Bakker 2008). Employee engagement is a powerful concept that organizations can utilize to improve many of their business functions, including safety performance. Some of the ways that employees can become involved in addressing the safety of the work in which they are going to be engaged may include participating in production goal assessment, having input into planning the work, assessing the risk, evaluating the procedures, suggesting possible practice methods, addressing logistics, selecting risk mitigation techniques, having the right information, etc. The organization have to select the right workers as well as supervisors, have staffs that are knowledgeable of the operational functions, and have a deep understanding of human nature. They will also have to enlightened leadership, a culture and climate that foster and support engagement and integrated and aligned organizational and operational systems. There has to be robust and open communication, fair treatment and feedback as well as opportunity for growth and development. The degree to which these aspects are implemented and function seamlessly will determine the level of engagement and the outcomes that drive the organization's success.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to analysis the healthcare sector employee's perception towards employee's engagement factors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Type of Design

Descriptive research design has been applied to this study. This design allows the researcher to describe the respondent's opinion towards the research objective.

Variable Considered for this Study

Employee's engagement factors such as meaningful at work, intrinsic rewards, extrinsic rewards, self-efficacy, departmental support, supervisor support, co-worker support, job autonomy and job security are confident as the study variables in this research. Questionnaire has been considered as the research tool for collecting primary data from the sample respondents.

Scaling Technique

In the questionnaire, all statements are measured in the likerts five points scale. Where 5 stands for strongly agree, 4-means agree, 3-means neither agree nor disagree, 2-means disagree and 1-mean strongly disagree.

Sampling Procedure

This study conducted among the health care professional working in the multi speciality hospital at Chennai. They are considered as the sample unit. A sample of 180 employees has been selected through convenience sampling mentioned. The sample comprised of administrative staff, allied health care employees and doctors.

Data Collection

The primary data have been collected from the sample respondents using a questionnaire.

Statistical Tools Used

In order to answer research objective, the collected primary data has been analysed with descriptive statistics such as near and standard deviation. It inference the employees level of opinion towards the study variables.

Table 1: Employee Opinion towards Meaningful Work

Meaningful Work	Mean	Std. Deviation
My job enables me to fulfill my potential and become a fully functioning person	3.54	1.31
My job creates Social status	3.60	1.39
My job enables me to fulfill my life purpose, goals and values	3.63	1.30
My job provides feelings of personal accomplishment	3.53	1.28
I belief in achieving my highest career goals in my organization	3.70	1.43

Source: Primary data computed.

Table - 1 explains the employee's opinion and importance towards meaningful work for employee engagement in the healthcare sector. Here, meaningful work is analyzed with five statements in the five point likert scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each factor. The mean values are ranged from 3.53 to 3.70. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 1.28 and 1.43. From the mean value, it is inferred that, the employees are highly rated towards their belief in achieving their highest career goals in the organization of meaningful work (3.70) followed by, their job enables to them fulfill in life purpose, goals and values (3.63), job creates social status (3.60), job enables to them fulfill their potential and become a fully functioning person (3.54) and also job provides feelings of personal accomplishment (3.53). From the standard deviation values, it is noted that the employees perception towards meaningful work is not varied as much. It is noted that the employees are highly rated that their belief in achieving and they are highest career goals in the organization of meaningful work.

Table 2: Employee Importance towards Intrinsic Rewards

Intrinsic Rewards	Mean	Std. Deviation
My skill is fully utilized	3.74	1.42
I have more task variety	3.50	1.34
My task identity is rewarded	3.52	1.19
I have creative freedom	3.75	1.33
I allowed to involve and participate in the organization achieving	3.76	1.38
I have general opportunities for growth and development	4.02	1.29

Source: Primary data computed.

Table - 2 shows the employees opinion and importance towards intrinsic rewards for employee engagement in the healthcare sectors. Here, intrinsic rewards is analyzed with six statements in the five point likert scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each factor. The mean values are ranged from 3.49 to 4.02. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 1.19 and 1.42. From the mean value, it is inferred that, the employees have general opportunities for growth and development in the organization of intrinsic rewards (4.02) followed by, allowed to them involve and participate in the organization achievement (3.76), have creative freedom (3.75), skill is fully utilized (3.74), employee task identity and rewarded to them (3.52) and also employee to have more task variety (3.49). From the standard deviation values, it is observed that the employee’s perception towards intrinsic reward is not varied as much.

It is inferred that the employees are highly rated that the they have general opportunities for growth and development in the organization of intrinsic reward.

Table 3: Employee Importance towards Extrinsic Rewards

Extrinsic Rewards	Mean	Std. Deviation
Fair pay	3.84	1.14
Perks	3.78	1.33
I rewarded by coupons	4.21	0.92
I rewarded by gifts	3.70	1.21
I rewarded by social party	3.60	1.41
I awarded by gold star	3.50	1.38

Source: Primary data computed.

Table - 3 portrays the employee’s opinion and importance towards extrinsic rewards for employee engagement in the healthcare sector. Here, extrinsic rewards is analyzed with six statements in the five point likert scale.

Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each statements. The mean values are ranged from 3.50 to 4.21. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 0.92 and 1.41.

From the mean value, it is inferred that, the employees have rewarded by coupons system in the organization towards extrinsic rewards (4.21) followed by, company providing good pay for employees (3.84), have good perks (3.78), rewarded by gifts (3.70), rewarded by social party (3.60) and awarded to employee with gold star, performance appreciations (3.50). From the standard deviation values, it is noted that the employee's perception towards extrinsic reward is not varied as much.

It is observed that the employees are highly rated that the they are rewarded by coupons system in the organization towards extrinsic rewards.

Table 4: Employee importance towards Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy	Mean	Std. Deviation
I have concern for personal excellence	3.70	1.28
I have concern for influence	4.31	0.94
I have concern for family	3.90	1.20
I have concern for others and society	3.56	1.37
I am awareness of personal strength	3.28	1.30
I am awareness of personal weakness	3.64	1.24
I am awareness of achievement	4.36	0.95
I have concern for self-development	3.99	1.24
I have internal locus of control	3.76	1.38
I have proactive orientation	3.26	1.26
I have self-discipline	3.54	1.28

Source: Primary data computed.

The result is displayed in the table - 4 the employee opinion and importance towards self-efficacy for employee engagement in the healthcare sector. Here, self-efficacy is analyzed with eleven statements in the five point likert scale.

Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each factor. The mean values are ranged from 3.26 to 4.36. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 0.94 and 1.38.

From the mean value, it is inferred that, the employees awareness of achievement in the organization towards self-efficacy (4.36) followed by, have concern for influence (4.31), have concern for self-development (3.99), have concern for family (3.90), have internal locus of control (3.76), have concern for personal excellence (3.70), awareness of personal weakness (3.64), have concern for others and society (3.56), have self-discipline (3.54), awareness of personal strength (3.28) and have proactive orientation (3.26).

From the standard deviation values, it is noted that the employee's perception towards self-efficacy is not varied as much. It is inferred that the employees awareness of achievement in the organization towards self-efficacy.

Table 5: Employee Importance towards Departmental Organizational Support

Perceived Departmental Support	Mean	Std. Deviation
The organization values my contribution to its well-being	4.16	0.90
If the organization could hire someone to replace me at a lower salary it would do so	4.11	1.29
The organization does not fails to appreciate any extra effort from me	3.76	1.40
The organization strongly considers my goals and values	3.51	1.38
The organization won't ignore any complaint from me	3.50	1.25
The organization heed my best interests when it makes decision that affect me	4.25	1.02
Help is available from the organization when I have a problem	3.59	1.23
The organization really cares about my well-being	3.67	1.45
The organization is willing to extent itself in order to help me perform my job to the best of my ability	3.24	1.27
Even if I did the best job possible, the organization won't fail to notice	3.58	1.40
The organization is willing to help me when I need a special favor	3.86	1.26
The organization cares about my general satisfaction at work	3.94	1.42
If given the opportunity, the organization won't take advantage of me	3.61	1.31
The organization shows more concern for me	3.44	1.44
The organization cares about my opinions	3.23	1.23
The organizations takes pride in my accomplishments at work	3.95	1.29
The organization tries to make my job as interesting as possible	3.73	1.32

Source: Primary data computed.

Table - 5 depicts the employee’s opinion and importance towards perceived organizational support for employee engagement in the healthcare sector. Here, perceived departmental support is analyzed with seventeen factors in the five point likert scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each factor. The mean values are ranged from 3.23 to 4.25. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 0.90 and 1.45. From the mean value, it is noted that, the organization need employee best interests when it makes decision that affect employee in the organization towards perceived organizational support (4.25) followed by, the organization values employee contribution to its well-being(4.16),If the organization could hire someone to replace employee at a lower salary it would do so (4.11), the organizations takes pride in employee accomplishments at work (3.95), the organization cares about employee general satisfaction at work (3.94), the organization is willing to help employee when they need a special favor (3.86), the organization does not fails to appreciate any extra effort from employees(3.76), the organization tries to make employees job as interesting as possible (3.73), the organization really cares about employee well-being (3.67), If given the opportunity, the organization won't take advantage of employees(3.61), help is available from the organization when employee have a problem(3.59), Even if employee did the best job possible, the organization won't fail to notice (3.58), the organization strongly considers employees goals and values (3.51), the organization won't ignore any complaint from employee (3.50), the organization shows more concern for employee(3.44), the organization is willing to extent itself in order to help employee perform their job to the best of their ability (3.24) and the organization cares about employees opinions(3.23). From the standard deviation

values, it is inferred that the employee’s perception towards perceived organizational support is not varied as much. It is observed that the organization need employee best interests when it makes decision that affect employee in the organization towards perceived organizational support.

Table 6: Employee Perceptions towards Supervisory Support

Supervisory support	Mean	Std. Deviation
My supervisor takes the time to learn about my career goals and aspirations	3.89	1.45
My supervisor cares about whether or not I achieve my goals.	3.23	1.19
My supervisor keeps me informed about different career opportunities for me in the organization	3.46	1.41
My supervisor makes sure I get the credit when I accomplish something substantial on the job	3.61	1.19
My supervisor gives me helpful feedback about my performance	3.81	1.35
My supervisor gives me helpful advice about improving my performance when I need it	3.78	1.39
My supervisor supports my attempts to acquire additional training or education to further my career	3.58	1.48
My supervisor provides assignments that give me the opportunity to develop and strengthen new skills	3.35	1.25
My supervisor assigns me special projects that increase my visibility in the organization	3.82	1.32

Source: Primary data computed.

Table - 8 shows that employees perception towards supervisor support in the healthcare sector. Here, supervisor support is analyzed with nine factors in the five point likert scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each factor. The mean values are ranged from 3.23 to 3.89. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 1.19 and 1.48. From the mean value, it is inferred that, the supervisor takes the time to learn about employees career goals and aspirations in the organization towards supervisor support (3.89) followed by, supervisor assigns special projects that increase their visibility in the organization (3.82), supervisor gives helpful feedback about their performance (3.81), supervisor gives helpful advice about improving employees performance when they need it (3.78), supervisor makes sure and get the credit when employee accomplish something substantial on the job (3.61), supervisor supports my attempts to acquire additional training or education to further employee career (3.58), supervisor keeps informed about different career opportunities for their in the organization (3.46), supervisor provides assignments that give the opportunity to develop and strengthen new skills (3.35) and supervisor cares about whether or not achieve their goals(3.28). From the standard deviation values, it is noted that the employee’s perception towards supervisor support is not varied as much. It is noted that the supervisor takes the time to learn about employee’s career goals and aspirations in the organization towards supervisor support.

Table 7: Employee opinion towards Co-worker Support

Co-worker Support	Mean	Std. Deviation
Trust worthy	3.45	1.23
Respectful	3.83	1.42
Emotional	3.36	1.32
Instrumental	3.90	1.39

Source: Primary data computed.

Table - 7 explain that the employee opinion towards co-support in the healthcare sectors. Here, co-support is analyzed with four factors in the five point likert scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each factor. The mean values are ranged from 3.36 to 3.90. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 1.23 and 1.42. From the mean value, it is inferred that, the instrument and machinery item in the organization towards co-worker support (3.90) followed by, co-worker respect in the organization (3.83),co-worker trust worthy in the organization (3.45), and emotional is play in co-worker support(3.36). From the standard deviation values, it is noted that the employee’s opinion towards co-support is not varied as much. It is pointed the supervisor takes the instrument and machinery item in the organization towards co-worker support.

Table 8: Employee Importance Level towards Job Autonomy

Job Autonomy	Mean	Std. Deviation
How much are you left on your own to do your own work	3.75	1.172
To what extent are you able to act independently of your supervisor in performing your job function	3.66	1.385
To what extent are you able to do your job independently of others	3.48	1.320
The freedom to do pretty much what I want on my job	3.43	1.382
The opportunity for independent thought and action	3.53	1.364
The control I have over the peace of my work	4.09	1.336

Source: Primary data computed.

Table - 8 depicts the employee’s importance level towards job autonomy for employee engagement in healthcare sector. Here, perceived job autonomy is analyzed with six factors in the five point likert scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each factor. The mean values are ranged from 3.43 to 4.09. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 1.17 and 1.38. From the mean value, it is noted that, the control and have over the peace of their work in the organization towards perceived job autonomy(4.09) followed by, How much are you left on your own to do your own work(3.75),what extent are you able to act independently of your supervisor in performing your job function(3.66),the opportunity for independent thought and action(3.53), what extent are you able to do your job independently of others (3.48) and the freedom to do pretty much what they want on employee job (3.43). From the standard deviation values, it is inferred that the employee’s perception towards perceived job autonomy is not varied as much. It is observed that the control and have over the peace of their work in the organization towards perceived job autonomy.

Table 9: Employee perception level towards Job security

Job security	Mean	Std. Deviation
Management has made an explicit commitment to employees to avoid lay off redundancies, except in extreme circumstances.	3.60	1.23
Disputes are always resolved fairly and impartially.	3.59	1.39
Employees are led to expect long-term employment in this organization.	3.25	1.27
I have a sense of job security working in this company.	3.58	1.40

Source: Primary data computed.

Table - 9 shows that employee perception towards job security in healthcare sector. Here, job security is analyzed with four factors in the five point likert scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each factor. The mean values are ranged from 3.25 to 3.60. The calculated standard deviation values lies between 1.23 and 1.40. From the mean value, it is noted that, the management has made an explicit commitment to employees and avoid lay off redundancies, except in extreme circumstances in the organization towards job security (3.60) followed by, disputes are always resolved fairly and impartially (3.59), have a sense of job security working in this company (3.58) and employees are led to expect long-term employment in this organization (3.25). From the standard deviation values, it is noted that the employee's perception towards job security is not varied as much. It is observed that the management has made an explicit commitment to employees and avoid lay off redundancies, except in extreme circumstances in the organization towards job security.

FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATION CONCLUSION

Employee's meaningful work has to be at moderate level. Here, employees believed that they are achieving their highest score goal in their organization found to be high. However employee's job provided feeling of personal accomplishment is found to be low. So, management provide to employee's personal accomplishment towards their job opportunities for growth and development is found to high for intrinsic reward. But, variety of task intrinsic reward found to be low. So employees may be intrinsic reward interms of task oriented. Coupons as a extrinsic reward is found to be high in the organization. But, extrinsic reward of gold star and social party are found to be low in the organization. So organization try to award to the extras performance to star award and allow them to have social get together. Self-efficacy found to be at moderate level. Here, employee have higher level of self-influence. However, proactive orientation and awareness of personal strength. So, employees should the proactive and have more awareness about their personal strength, departmental support is found to be high. But, supervisor support and co-worker support found to be at average level. Hence, the management try to inculcate the supervisor support and co-worker support.

This can be done through right selection of candidates, proper training, power sharing, work-information sharing, knowledge or employee skills and performance rewards system. How high-involvement work practices can contribute in effective employee engagement. High involvement work practices are the techniques used by the management to efficiently involve their employees in their works and receive high performance among employees.

If there is no career progression or limited career advancement opportunities, then employees will definitely be disengaged at certain level and shall not remain committed with an organization. Organization's repute as a good employer, availability of resources needed to perform job in high quality and communication of clear vision for long term success by the higher management are also critical factors in building employee engagement.

Hence, employee engagement is today seen as a powerful source of competitive advantage in the turbulent times. The study explores the concept of employee engagement and also throws light on key drivers of employee engagement by analyzing specifically three drivers, namely communication, work life balance and leadership.

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